

GENAI MULTIPLE: THE INFLUENCE OF GENERATIVE AI COMPONENTS IN BUSINESS MODELS ON COMPANY VALUATION

Bukhtueva Irina

*bachelor's degree, Lomonosov Moscow State University
Leninskie Gory, 1, Moscow, 119991, Russian Federation*

Abstract

This article analyzes the influence of multiple generative artificial intelligence (GenAI multiple) components on business models and company valuation. The main aspects of using GenAI multiple are considered, such as process automation, reducing operating costs, improving forecasting accuracy and improving customer interaction. Special attention is given to the study of synergistic interactions between multiple artificial intelligence models for process optimization, which opens up new opportunities for companies in industries like finance, marketing, retail, and manufacturing. The article also discusses how GenAI multiple contributes to the growth of intangible company assets, such as data and intellectual property, thus increasing their market value. Examples of successful implementation of GenAI multiple by companies like Accenture and Bain & Company are provided.

Keywords: multiple generative artificial intelligence (GenAI multiple), business models, company valuation, automation, intellectual property, forecasting, operational costs.

Introduction

Multiple generative artificial intelligence (GenAI multiple) is one of the most promising and rapidly evolving fields within artificial intelligence (AI). Traditional singular AI systems, such as GPT or Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN), have proven effective in solving specific tasks like text generation, image creation, or forecasting. However, the increasing complexity of modern business models requires more flexible and multifunctional solutions, leading to the emergence of GenAI multiple, which integrates various generative approaches into one system to perform different functions simultaneously.

Implementing GenAI multiple into business processes significantly enhances companies' operational efficiency by reducing costs and optimizing the handling of large data volumes. Its application is especially relevant in industries such as finance, marketing, retail, and manufacturing, where highly efficient processing of heterogeneous data is required to make strategic decisions. One of the most important aspects of using GenAI multiple is its impact on company valuation. Integrating several AI models into a business model can

increase a company's capitalization by improving processes, optimizing resource use, and creating new revenue streams. Intellectual property related to the development and application of GenAI multiple increases the value of a company's intangible assets, making it more attractive to investors. The purpose of this article is to explore the influence of GenAI multiple components on business models and company valuation.

Main part. Theoretical foundations of GenAI multiple

The architecture in which multiple independent generative models work together to solve complex tasks is referred to as GenAI multiple. The expanding scope of technology applications, including super-resolution, text-to-image and text-to-video transformation, and the modernization of workflows across industries, drives the demand for generative AI applications in sectors such as media and entertainment, retail, manufacturing, IT, and telecommunications. In 2023, the global generative AI market was valued at USA 13,0 billion, and it is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 36,5% from 2024 to 2030 (pic. 1).

Pic. 1. Global GenAI market size, billion USA dollars [1]

There are several features of GenAI multiple that distinguish it from other AI technologies. Its main advantage lies in its ability to **combine several models**, each capable of performing individual tasks, which makes the system more powerful and flexible. While single AI systems typically focus on performing one specialized task, GenAI multiple integrates various models such as text and visual generators, language models, and predictive systems, allowing it to process different types of data and solve diverse tasks simultaneously. This greatly expands the applicability of GenAI multiple, making it adaptable to various scenarios.

The introduction of GenAI multiple allows for the effective use of synergistic interactions between models. One model may process text, another generates images, while a third analyzes data and predicts outcomes, providing a **comprehensive approach to task execution**. This architecture enables higher accuracy and quality of the generated content, as each model operates in its specialized domain. The use of GenAI multiple is indispensable for tasks requiring multimodal data processing – text, images, sound and video. Another important feature of the system is its flexibility and scalability. The models within GenAI multiple can be easily replaced or supplemented with new ones, allowing the system to evolve as new technologies and requirements emerge [2]. This gives businesses the ability to adapt quickly to market changes by introducing new models that provide additional functionality and increase productivity. The distributed nature of computation among different models makes the system more **efficient in terms of resource utilization**, which is especially important when handling large volumes of data.

Thus, GenAI multiple stands out for its enhanced functionality, flexibility, and ability to solve complex tasks, making it a valuable tool for businesses. However, its successful implementation requires careful planning and management, considering the complexity of model interactions and the system's resource-intensive nature.

The main components of GenAI multiple and their application in business models

Being a complex technological system, GenAI multiple includes several main components, each of which plays an important role in its functioning and integration into business models. The core elements of

the GenAI multiple system include text and visual generators, data processing tools, and language models. These components are actively used for automating processes, creating content, and analyzing data, opening new opportunities for companies seeking to increase efficiency and innovation.

Text generators are models used to create textual content. They can automatically generate articles, scripts, dialogues, marketing materials, and other types of text. In the context of GenAI multiple, text generators can interact with other models, such as visual or predictive systems, to create comprehensive results, such as multimedia content or forecasts with textual explanations. This is particularly relevant for companies working in media, e-commerce, and marketing, where large volumes of content need to be created quickly [3].

Visual generators create graphic and visual content. They are widely used to generate images, videos, and other visual elements. In the framework of GenAI multiple, visual generators can be used in combination with text models to automatically generate marketing campaigns or complex graphic materials.

Language models play an important role in natural language processing. These models are trained on large volumes of textual data and can analyze, interpret, and generate text. One of the important applications of language models is the automation of customer interactions, allowing companies to quickly process queries, provide consultations, and resolve issues in real time. They also play a crucial role in service personalization, capable of analyzing large amounts of customer data, such as purchase history, preferences, and behavior, to create personalized offers.

Predictive systems are used for data analysis and forecasting based on historical data. In business, predictive systems improve decision-making processes by predicting future market trends, demand fluctuations, or consumer behavior. In GenAI multiple, they can integrate with other components, providing the analytical basis for automated decisions.

The application of GenAI multiple is becoming one of the most significant factors influencing the transformation of modern business models. Tools based on it offer companies new opportunities to increase operational efficiency, create innovative products, and improve customer interactions. The main advantages are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Advantages of using GenAI multiple in business models [4, 5]

Aspect	Description	Application example
Improving the quality of results	Improving the accuracy and efficiency of solutions by utilizing multiple models for various tasks.	Using multiple AI models to process texts, images, and data simultaneously.
Flexibility and scalability	It easily adapts to new conditions and tasks, providing wider business use opportunities.	It is used in various industries such as finance, retail, manufacturing and marketing.
Automation of processes	Automation of content creation, data analysis and other business processes with minimal human involvement.	Automatic generation of reports and recommendations based on data, improving customer interactions.
Reducing operating costs	Reducing labor costs and transaction expenses through the automation of routine processes.	Reducing the cost of data processing and maintaining client services.
Improving the accuracy of forecasts	Accurate forecasts help to better plan resources and adapt to changes in the market.	Demand forecasting, inventory management and improvement of production chains.
Creation of new products and services	Promotes the development of innovative products and services by combining data and generative models.	Development of personalized products in retail and innovative solutions in fintech.

The use of GenAI multiple components in business models allows companies to improve many aspects of their operations. Automating content creation, data analysis, forecasting, and optimizing operational processes lead to increased efficiency and reduced costs. Implementing such technologies makes companies more competitive, enabling them to adapt quickly to changing market conditions and provide more personalized and innovative products and services.

The impact of GenAI on company valuation

One of the factors stimulating the economic growth of companies in various sectors is generative artificial intelligence (GenAI). Its implementation transforms business processes, improves operational efficiency, and creates new revenue streams, all of which significantly affect a company's valuation.

The integration of GenAI **significantly impacts the economic performance of companies by boosting productivity and reducing costs**. Automating business processes, such as content creation, data analysis, and customer service, speeds up task completion and reduces the need for human resources. For example, text and visual generators can replace manual labor in creating marketing materials or personalized offers, thus reducing labor costs. The implementation of GenAI also optimized internal processes using predictive models for data analysis, which improved inventory management, production planning and reduced logistics costs. As a result, companies can not only increase efficiency but also significantly lower operational expenses. This effect is directly reflected in the company's financial performance, increasing profitability and return on investment, which in turn positively influences the overall company valuation.

Companies that actively integrate GenAI into their business models often **experience increased capitalization**. This is because the use of advanced AI technologies is seen by the market and investors as a factor that enhances competitiveness and long-term growth prospects. Investors see potential in technologies that enable companies to automate processes, adapt quickly to market changes, and create innovative products [6].

Additionally, GenAI has a strong impact on **the valuation of a company's intangible assets**, such as data and intellectual property. In the digital age, data has become one of the most valuable company assets, and GenAI allows for effective data use to create new solutions and products. Companies with large datasets and those using GenAI to process and analyze them can significantly enhance the value of their data. AI-driven data analysis enables better understanding of customer behavior, optimization of business processes, and improved service quality, which strengthens a company's market position.

Intellectual property related to the development of GenAI technologies plays an important role in the valuation of companies. Companies that develop unique AI models or hold patents on generative technologies can significantly increase their valuation due to the growing value of these assets. Investments in intellectual property not only increase the market value of a company but also protect innovations from competitors. Thus, GenAI contributes to the growth of intangible assets by increasing the value of data and developing unique technologies, which is directly reflected in the company's overall valuation.

In a rapidly changing market environment, investors increasingly view companies actively adopting AI as more promising and resilient. Technologies using GenAI help companies automate core processes, reducing the risks associated with human error, and increasing flexibility and adaptability in a competitive environment. Companies that adopt GenAI demonstrate readiness for digital transformation, which is an important indicator for investors. These companies are seen as innovative and technologically advanced organizations, attracting more attention from venture capital funds and strategic investors. For example, technology startups that use GenAI to create unique products and solutions have a high chance of receiving significant investments at early development stages. Companies using GenAI show a high likelihood of long-term growth, as they can better adapt to market changes and quickly

implement innovations. This makes them especially attractive to long-term investors seeking stable and high returns on investments in promising technologies.

An example of successful application of GenAI is the experience of **Accenture**, which actively uses these technologies to accelerate the digital transformation of its customers, offering solutions that include automation of processes using generative models. For example, Accenture helps large technology companies automate content creation using text and visual generators. This speeds up the process of preparing reports, advertising campaigns and multimedia materials [7].

Deloitte, one of the Big Four companies, uses GenAI to automate data analysis processes in the financial sector. For example, Deloitte uses predictive models to identify financial risks and predict market trends, which helps banks and investment companies minimize risks and increase profitability [8].

Another example is the experience of **Bain & Company** that uses GenAI to optimize supply chains and forecast demand in retail and manufacturing. It implements predictive models that help customers predict changes in demand based on analysis of historical data and current market trends. This allows retailers and manufacturers to better manage inventory, reduce storage and logistics costs, and improve delivery accuracy [9].

Companies from Accenture, Bain and Big4 are actively using GenAI multiple to optimize business processes in various industries. In the technology sector, GenAI accelerates digital transformation, in the financial sector it reduces risks and automates data analysis, and in retail and manufacturing it helps to predict demand and improve supply chain management.

Conclusion

As a powerful tool capable of transforming modern business models, GenAI significantly influences company valuation. Its implementation provides new opportunities for automation, process optimization, and operational efficiency across various sectors, from technology and finance to retail and manufacturing. Important components of GenAI, such as text and visual generators, language models and forecasting systems, contribute to improving the quality of business decisions, reducing costs and creating innovative products and services.

The economic impact of GenAI is evident in increased productivity and significantly reduced operating costs. This enables companies to strengthen their market positions and increase capitalization by improving financial performance and creating intellectual property based on AI technologies. The impact on intangible assets such as data and intellectual property is especially important because in the digital age, they are becoming important factors in creating company value. The use of GenAI multiple also increases the investment attractiveness of companies, as artificial intelligence technologies are perceived as a long-term source of growth and competitive advantage.

Overall, companies that successfully integrate GenAI into their business models not only optimize their operational processes but also enhance their market value. The development and use of these technologies open up opportunities for further innovation, improving business outcomes and creating new growth opportunities in a rapidly changing economic landscape.

References

1. The volume of the global generative artificial intelligence (AI) market in the period from 2020 to 2030 / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1449838/generative-ai-market-size-worldwide> (date of application 20.09.2024)
2. Mozharovskii E. Integration of Large Language Models (LLM) into mobile applications // Innovative Approaches in Modern Science: Collection of Articles from the Materials of the CLIX International Scientific and Practical Conference «Innovative Approaches in Modern Science». – No. 3(159). – Moscow, Publishing House «Internauka», 2024.
3. Kanbach D. K., Heiduk L., Blueher G., Schreiter M., Lahmann A. The GenAI is out of the bottle: generative artificial intelligence from a business model innovation perspective // Review of Managerial Science. 2024. V. 18. №. 4. P. 1189-1220.
4. Korostin O. Forecasting market trends in maritime shipping based on big data analysis // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. 2024. V. 137. № 9. P. 12-15.
5. Mariani M., Dwivedi Y. K. Generative artificial intelligence in innovation management: A preview of future research developments // Journal of Business Research. 2024. V. 175. P. 114542.
6. Pshychenko D. Development and analysis of algorithms for solving specific business tasks using AI // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. 2024. V. 137(09). P. 31-36.
7. Accenture Invests in Writer to Accelerate Enterprise Use of Generative AI // URL: <https://newsroom.accenture.com/news/2023/accenture-invests-in-writer-to-accelerate-enterprise-use-of-generative-ai> (date of application 17.09.2024).
8. Bruno M., Skoglund K. Analyzing the themes of Artificial Intelligence as framed by the Big Four accounting firms: A Document Analysis. 2024.
9. Generative AI virtually ubiquitous in global business as the technology spreads at a near-unprecedented rate — Bain & Company proprietary survey / Bain & Company // URL: <https://www.bain.com/about/media-center/press-releases/2024/generative-ai-virtually-ubiquitous-in-global-business-as-the-technology-spreads-at-a-near-unprecedented-rate--bain--company-proprietary-survey/#:~:text=Bain's%20latest%20proprietary%20cross-industry%20Generative%20AI> (date of application 17.09.2024).